

USING NEW TECHNIQUE TO DETERMINE POWER OF LENS

A. H. Abdelrahman^{1,2}

¹Laser system Department, Laser Institute, SUST, Khartoum, Sudan

²Department of Physics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Al-Munzab, Qassim University, KSA

*Author for Correspondence

ABSTRACT

In this work, a formula relating to the strength of the apparent source formed by any type of optical system proved dependent on the refraction properties of this system. Confining ourselves to lenses shows that the strength of the apparent source depends on its focal length. The intensity of this apparent source was found to be inversely proportional to the square of the distance. This theoretical relation verified experimentally. It was also noticed that the empirical relation is in conformity with the theoretical one. These relations were utilized to determine the lens power in terms of apparent source intensity.

Key Words: Optics, Lens and Optical Power

INTRODUCTION

The intensity of light plays an important role in our daily life (Vandergriff, 1999). This may be attributed to the fact that our sense of vision stimulated by light. The control of light intensity is extremely essential for an appropriate vision. Lighting is an essential provision for any workplace (Serway, 2005). The luminance level ranges from 10^{-3} cd/m² to 3cd/m² for an appropriate vision (Abrams, 1985 and Agarwal, 1979).

THE INTENSITY OF THE APPARENT SOURCE FORMED BY OPTICAL SYSTEM

Usually there is a relation between the optical and original source through what is known as transmittance (T). The (T) is the ratio of the luminous emerges from the optical system to the luminous flux per unit area incident on the optical system i.e. (Klein & Furtak, 1986)

$$T = \frac{(E_e)}{(E_i)} \quad (1)$$

Where E_e , E_i refers to luminous flux per unit area emergent from the optical system and luminous flux per unit area emergent from the optical system, respectively (Bennett & Rabbett, 1997; Singh, 2013; Taylor, 2000).

To find this relation one can consider the general case when a light is incident from a source of luminous intensity E , at a distance r_i from the optical system, with incident angle (φ_i); in this case the emergent beam can be considered as emerging from an apparent source of intensity E' (Fowler & Petre, 2001; Ballard et al., 1954). The intensity E' can be obtained in terms of the distance r_e of the apparent source from the optical system and the angle of emergence (φ_e) fig. (1) Clearly shows that.

Figure 1: Incident and emergence light on the optical system

According to the definition of illumination, in terms of the source having luminous intensity E , and distance r on one side, and the luminous flux per unit area Φ/A , the illumination, I_i , at the incidence surface of the optical system is given below (Agarwal, 1979; Taylor, 2000):

$$I_i = \frac{E \cos(\theta_i)}{r_i^2} = \frac{\varphi_i}{A_i} \quad (2)$$

Research Article

Similarly, the illumination I_e at the emergence surface takes the form

$$I_e = \frac{E' \cos(\theta_e)}{r_e^2} = \frac{\phi_e}{A_e} \quad (3)$$

Inserting equation (2) and (3) in equation (1) one gets

$$T = X\% = \frac{X}{100} = \frac{I_e}{I_i} = \frac{r_i^2 E' \cos(\theta_e)}{r_e^2 E \cos(\theta_i)} \quad (4)$$

$$E' = \frac{X \cos(\theta_i)}{100 \cos(\theta_e)} \left(\frac{r_e}{r_i}\right)^2 E \quad (5)$$

In the case of normal incidence $\theta_i = \theta_e = 0^\circ$, the apparent source intensity can thus, given as:

$$E' = \frac{X}{100} \left(\frac{r_e}{r_i}\right)^2 E \quad (6)$$

THE INTENSITY OF THE APPARENT SOURCE FORMED BY A LENS

Since lenses are widely used to control light distribution and intensity, it is thus interesting to determine the luminous intensity of the apparent source E' for lenses (Fowler & Petre, 2001; Ballard et al., 1954; Goss & West, 2002; Smith, 1966). In view of equation (5), r_i and r_e stand for the object distance u and the image distance v respectively as shown in fig. 2.

As a result, the luminous intensity E' of the apparent source is shown as under:

$$E' = \frac{X}{100} \left(\frac{v}{u}\right)^2 E = \frac{X}{100} m^2 E \quad (7)$$

Where $m = v/u$ represents the magnification of the lens under consideration

Figure 2: Object distance u and the image distance v from lens

But since the image distance v cannot be measured easily, it is convenient to express magnification m in terms of the focal length f and the object distance u , where (Kingslake, 1965; Katz, 1981; Rea, 1993);

$$\frac{1}{v} = \frac{1}{f} - \frac{1}{u} = \frac{u - f}{uf} \quad (8)$$

Hence, the magnification m is given by

$$m = \frac{v}{u} = \frac{f}{u - f} \quad (9)$$

UTILIZING APPARENT SOURCE TO FIND THE FOCAL LENGTH AND THE LENS POWER

The notion of the apparent source can be widely used in many applications. One of the most interesting applications is to find the focal length and power of a lens. To see how this can be done, consider a parallel paraxial ray's incident on a lens of focal length f . According to the laws of geometrical optics the emergent beam converges at a focal point forming an apparent source of luminous intensity E' (Ballard et al., 1954; Thall, 1996; Stephens & Davis, 1993). The illumination (luminous flux density) I' at any arbitrary point r' from the source E' is:

$$I' = \frac{E'^2}{r'^2} \quad (10)$$

The distance r' is related to the focal length f according to the relation

$$r' = f + L \quad (11)$$

Research Article

where L stands for the distance between the lens and the point under consideration. In view of equations (8) and (9) one gets:

$$I' = \frac{E'^2}{(f + L)^2} \quad (12)$$

Rearranging this equation to put it in the standard linear form

$$Y = ax + b \quad (13)$$

yields

$$f + L = \frac{E'}{\sqrt{I'}} \Rightarrow L = \frac{E'}{\sqrt{I'}} - f \quad (14)$$

Hence,,one can easily find the focal length by taking different readings for E' at different locations L, and draw a graph in which L is represented on the y axis and $1/\sqrt{E'}$ on the x- axis, where direct comparison of (11) and (12) indicates that:

$$Y \equiv L, \quad x \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{I'}} , \quad a \equiv E' , \quad b \equiv -f \quad (15)$$

This means that the focal length f and the lens power can be obtained from the intercept b., which obtain from the relation as seen in fig. (3)

Figure 3: The relation between $\frac{1}{\sqrt{I'}}$ and location (L)

Below are the focal length and focal power;

$$f = -b, \quad P = -1/b \quad (16)$$

EXPERIMENTAL SET UP AND MEASUREMENTS

To find the focal length and power according to the lens, the relations (12), (13) and (14) were used. An experiment is conducted with an optical bench of one-meter length, beside a very small lamp mounted at a focal point of a lens of focal length f_0 to produce a parallel beam which is allowed to incident on the lens which we need to find its focal length as shown in fig (4).

Figure 4: Shown an optical system used to obtain an optical power of lenses

To verify relation (12) and to see whether it can be utilized as a tool to find optical power of lenses, 5 concave spherical lenses from a standard set used. The powers of these lenses are -4, -5, -7, -10, -11 respectively.

Research Article

RESULTS

In view of relations (12) and (13), different readings for the luminance (I) are obtained for different positions (L) as shown in the following 5 tables. The corresponding focal lengths and powers are obtained with the aid of equation (14).

Table 1: Shown luminance (I) corresponding to different distances (L) from lens (P: -4.00D.Sph)

L	I	\sqrt{I}	$1/\sqrt{I}$
20	31.1	5.576	0.179
25	28.8	5.366	0.186
30	23.8	4.878	0.204
35	16.4	4.049	0.246
40	14.1	3.754	0.266
45	15.1	3.885	0.257
50	12.0	3.464	0.288

Figure 5: Shown an L versus $1/\sqrt{I}$ for lens (P: -4.00D.Sph)

Table 2: Shown luminance (I) corresponding to different distances (L) from lens (P: -5.00D.Sph)

L	I	\sqrt{I}	$1/\sqrt{I}$
20	26.2	5.118	0.195
25	24.2	4.919	0.203
30	19.5	4.415	0.226
35	13.2	3.633	0.275
40	11.0	3.316	0.301
45	11.6	3.405	0.293
50	9.2	3.033	0.329

Figure 6: Shown an L versus $1/\sqrt{I}$ for lens (P: -5.00D.Sph)

Research Article

Table 3: Shown luminance (I) corresponding to different distances (L) from lens (P: -7.00D.Sph)

L	I	\sqrt{I}	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{I}}$
20	17.9	4.230	0.236
25	15.8	3.974	0.251
30	12.4	3.521	0.283
35	8.5	2.915	0.342
40	7.1	2.664	0.375
45	6.8	2.607	0.383
50	5.6	2.366	0.422

Figure 7: Shown an L versus $\frac{1}{\sqrt{I}}$ for lens (P: -7.00D.Sph)

Table 4: Shown luminance (I) corresponding to different distances (L) from lens (P: -10.00D.Sph)

L	I	\sqrt{I}	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{I}}$
20	18.5	4.30	0.023
25	13.1	3.62	0.028
30	9.6	3.16	0.032
35	8.3	2.88	0.035
40	6.3	2.51	0.040
45	5.8	2.41	0.041
50	5.1	2.26	0.044

Figure 8: Shown an L versus $\frac{1}{\sqrt{I}}$ for lens (P: -10.00D.Sph)

Research Article

Table 5: Shown luminance (I) corresponding to different distances (L) from lens (P:-11.00D.Sph)

L	I	\sqrt{I}	$1/\sqrt{I}$
20	9.5	3.082	0.342
25	7.1	2.660	0.375
30	5.0	2.236	0.447
35	4.9	2.144	0.466
40	4.0	2.00	0.500
45	2.7	2.643	0.608

Figure 9: Shown an L versus $1/\sqrt{I}$ for lens (P: -11.00D.Sph)

Table 6: Shown the comparison between the actual and calculated power of some of the Standard English set lenses

Calculated Power	-2.45	-4.547	-5.819	-7.262	-9.25	-10.90	-11.27	-12.42	-18.73
Actual Power	-2.00	-4.00	-5.00	-7.00	-10.00	-10.00	-11.00	-12.00	-18.00

CONCLUSION

The empirical value of f and P for the five lenses is compared with their actual values. It shows that the values found by the intensity method are comparable with the actual values. The discrepancies may be attribute to the experimental errors arising from the fact that the small lamp is not an ideal point source so that the emergent beam from it is not exactly parallel. There is other experimental error, which are beyond the scope of this paper. An experiment is conducted to find the empirical relation between the intensity of the apparent source and the distance between the source and the point under consideration. This empirical relation is compare with the theoretical relation for the apparent source.

REFERENCES

Abrams D (1985). Duck Elder's Practice of Refraction. Churchill Livingstone.
Agarwal LP (1979). Principles of Optics and Refraction. CBS Publishers and Distributors.
Ballard SB, Slack EP & Hausmann E (1954). Physics Principles. D. Van Nostrand Company, NewYork.
Bennett AG & Rabbett RB (1997). Clinical Visual Optics, Butterworth-Heinemann.
Fowler C & Petre KL (2001). Spectacle Lenses: Theory and Practice. Butterworth-Heinemann 7-11.
Goss DA & West RW (2002). Introduction to the Optics of the Eye, Butterworth-Heinemann 8-11, 30-32, 141, 143
Katz M (1981). In Duane's Clinical Ophthalmology, The Human Eye as an Optical System, Volume 1, Lippincott-Raven Publishers.
Kingslake R (1965). Applied Optics and Optical Engineering. Academic Press New York.

Research Article

Klein MV & Furtak TE (1986). Optics. John Wiley & Sons.

Rea M (1993). Lighting Handbook. 8th Edition Illuminating Engineering Society of North America, New York.

Serway R (2005). Physics for Scientists and Engineers, 7th Edition Saunders College Publishing.

Singh B (2013). Illumination Basic & Scheme, Senior Lecturer Electrical Engg. Government Polytechnic College, Guru TegBahadurgarh, Moga.

Smith WJ (1966). Modern Optical Engineering. McGraw Hill New York.

Stephens GL & Davis JK (1993). In Duane's Clinical Ophthalmology (chapter 51) Spectacle Lenses, Volume 1, Lippincott-Raven Publishers.

Taylor AEF (2000). Illumination Fundamentals, Research Center; Dr. William Cassarly and Stuart David of Optical Research Associates.

Thall E (1996). In Duane's Clinical Ophthalmology, Geometrical Optics, Vol. 1, Lippincott- Raven Publishers.

Vandergriff LJ (1999). Fundamentals of Photonics. Laser Focus World.